

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OKELLO****FIRST NAME: PATRICK****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The basic principles of essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 6-13)
3. The difference between British and American English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
4. Proper use of commas, possessions in academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 18-23)
5. Writing style (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. Citation (EUCLID 2019, 6-12)
7. Rules of thumb in writing papers (EUCLID 2019, 14-15)

ACA-401/ACA-401D PERIOD 1

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D introduced me to the expected standards, steps, and key concepts in academic paper writing. It addressed the nature of an academic essay, the importance of giving credit to scholarly information sources, conducting a quick and effective literature review, and critical thumb rules in paper writing. The course pack further explained the difference between British and US English. This difference can cause inconsistencies and confusion in academic papers due to variations in spellings, meanings, punctuations, and use between the two. As a doctoral student, Euclid University will require that I produce academic papers that meet international publication and use standards. The course pack has clarified that an academic essay should answer a question or task, have a thesis statement, and an argument (EUCLID 2019, 1). It should also seek to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence, examples from academic texts, or credible sources discussed based on a set of related arguments (ibid.). Though I am used to British English, I have often confused British English with US English, and I am glad to have known this early as I start this career path that demands perfection and adherence to international scholarly standards.

2) REACTIONS TO THE STUDY MATERIAL

a) **First Point Explained**

Essay writing is one of the ways of documenting, sharing, and storing academic information. Although basic essay writing steps exist, these steps may be re-walked several times before completion (ibid.). Indeed, essay writing needs time, thinking, research, reading for persuasive writing. I find the explanations on essay writing steps reassuring immensely to new students like myself that, though not easy, someone can still write an excellent academic essay with dedication. Early preparation and reading provide an opportunity to identify and compile a body of credible evidence and examples that may help persuade readers to an idea or point of view.

Additionally, it is vital in academic writings where the need for impeccable evidence is beyond question to generate arguments supporting a thesis, especially in medicine. As a new student, I have taken the advice of starting early and reading widely in a very positive sense. Contrary to my old belief that an essay is written from top to bottom, I have learned that essay writing should start from the body, and the introduction and conclusion written last.

I found the presentation on the rules of thumb for writing papers very helpful. EUCLID emphasized the importance of stating the main thesis at or near the document's beginning (2019, 14). I find this very vital in capturing the attention of prospective readers from the onset of the paper. EUCLID also guides that the writer should remain focused on critically assessing some aspect of the theory to identify valid evidence and examples to support related arguments in favor of the writer's point of view (ibid.). The advice to guard against including, leading, or concluding with sweeping generalization is very relevant to my course (EUCLID 2019, 14)

I had experienced strong temptations to write long sentences that attempt to explain a whole idea in the past. I have learned that this is not necessary. Sentences should be clear and short, less than five lines, and less than 20 lines for paragraphs (EUCLID 2019, 15). It is necessary to include stylistic variety into the writing and strong support for assertions by introducing evidence for the attribution. The reminder to take the views being discussed in the paper seriously has caught my attention (ibid.). It is often much more comfortable to assume and take a simplistic view that the other writers are incorrect in their points of view. I am impressed by the guidance to treat any perceived 'foolish' ideas from other scholars as misconceptions. In most cases, these scholars invest a lot of time and energy to reach those opinions you may have considered unreasonable! I have learned to take a default position of respect for every scholar who contributes to the body of knowledge; recognizing that knowledge evolves with time, especially in the medical field

b) Second Point Explained

According to Dr. Yam Bahadur Roko, plagiarism originated from the Latin word ‘plagiarus,’ which means a kidnapper. It was first described by a dramatist Ben Jonson in 1601 to identify someone guilty of literacy theft (Bahadur 2017, 2). The primary motivations for plagiarism are the inherent desire or pressure to be successful, aggressive nature towards success, fear of discrimination or failure, and the need to increase the number of recorded publications (ibid.). For most students, it is likely the fear of failure that is more tempting towards plagiarism. I find the explanations on the concept of plagiarism fundamental in recognizing scholars’ hard work and contributions and promoting academic integrity. EUCLID (2019) explains that taking someone’s ideas or words and not giving credit to the author amounts to a serious intellectual crime [plagiarism] (5). The chapter on plagiarism further explains the importance of mentioning the sources of scholarly information used. Plagiarism sounds simple, but it exists in many forms: collisional, ghost, mosaic, self-plagiarism, source plagiarism, texts, words, and data plagiarism. Though efforts to reducing plagiarism are underway, including software such as iThenticate, many more approaches against plagiarism need to be deployed. The exact prevalence of plagiarism is unknown but estimated at 11-19% (Bahadur 2017, 2).

I find the explanation on when to cite, when not to cite, how to cite, and the use of quotations and paraphrases particularly crucial for my future scholarly work. The use of signal phrases was incredibly exciting as it introduces another style that requires only page numbers in parenthesis for the in-text citation.

c) Third Point Explained

Explanations of the difference between American and British English came in at the right time for me in this course. Having received most of my academic instructions in British English, I have often become confused about some aspects of American English. Some of the differences between British and American English are; the same spelling-different pronunciations, same pronunciations- different spellings, same form with similar but different accents and spellings, same words but different meanings. There are also differences in grammar, punctuations, and syntax (EUCLID 2019, 28). Another difference is the use of large collective nouns, whereas, in American English, they are singular but plural in British English (EUCLID 2019, 29).

Pensalfini, in his article titled ‘The Americans are destroying the English language – or are they? Published on the conversation website argues that;

First of all, nobody’s ruining the English language. And for anyone to call it “our” language is repugantly colonial. Language spreads, and language changes. English is spoken across the globe by more people (as a first, second, or foreign language) than any other and has the third-highest number of native speakers (only Mandarin and Spanish having more)

The fundamental difference between American and British English is essential to respect and follow, especially by us, the students who would love to have our scholarly work published. Therefore, it is crucial to adapt to the prospective editor and publisher's format to avoid last-minute corrections.

d) Fourth Point Explained

I found the guidance to join two clauses with a comma and conjunction quite different from what I knew. I had learned that there might be no need for a comma whenever a conjunction is joining two clauses. I have now appreciated that for purposes of clarity, the writer may use a comma. Additionally, my confusion on the difference between the possessive and contraction form of 'it' has been well explained. The ISO 8601 standard has cleared the mess I had regarding the British and American formats of date in technical fields that specify Year, Month, and Date format. This format avoids confusion between American and British dates (EUCLID 2019, 35).

However, the guidance on the need to spell out numbers at the beginning of a sentence is constructive though not clearly explained.

e) Fifth point explained

I found the concept of writing style exciting, explained as a means of documenting basic rules or writing features, allowing consistency in writing in specific fields (EUCLID 2019, 24). EUCLID recommends the Turabian style with clear guidance for both in-text citation and a list of books (ibid.). Holgate Library Research Guides explains that the Turabian style was developed especially for students by Kate Turabian, the dissertation secretary at the University of Chicago, and based on the Chicago writing style. According to EUCLID, writing style includes punctuations, grammar, vocabulary, preferred sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, spellings, abbreviations, use of symbols, use of the list, and others (25). My impression is that a writing style specifies the character and structure of scholarly work in a field. I now understand why many writing styles exist for different Universities and disciplines.

3) CONCLUSION

The course material presented clearly in sufficient detail nature, steps, style, and critical academic writing concepts with which I engaged. The explanation of plagiarism, the difference between American and British English, was crucial in erasing the long-standing confusion I had on both. The Grammarly software was incredibly helpful in correcting grammatical errors. Although I have not yet used Zotero much, I believe I will understand it better as the course progresses. This paper, ACA-401D period one, has exposed me to the extent of concentration required for this course. I am, therefore, more prepared mentally to tackle future periods and courses.

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